

The Development Strategy of Quail Farming Business in Pesantren Manajer Tholabie, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Pesantren Manajer Tholabie is Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia that has business units in the field of animal husbandry, the business of quail farming. The quail farming business in boarding school is expected to have a good economic impact and social impact on students and boarding school management. The purpose of this study was to formulate a development strategy for quail farming in boarding school starting in 2022. The method used was descriptive quantitative using SWOT analysis as data analysis. The results of this study show that the quail farming business has a significant impact on the boarding school, such as increasing cash income, providing education and additional skills for students, and adding community and stakeholder relations for the boarding school. The right strategy to develop the quail farming business is a collaboration of SWOT (Strengths-Weakness-Opportunities-Threats) strategies, which is using strengths and taking advantage of opportunities to minimize threats and improve weaknesses.

KEYWORDS: Economic Impact, Farmers, Pesantren, Poultry, SWOT, Socio Impact.

INTRODUCTION

Quail eggs are unique compared to other eggs, having a small size and having a black spot on the surface makes this egg easy to recognize the difference. The human body needs nutrients, one of which can be fulfilled from quail egg products. According to Listiyowati and Roositasari (2005), some of the contents in quail eggs such as calories, iron, fat, protein, phosphorus, vitamin A, vitamin B and vitamin B12 are known to be better than fresh cow's milk. Quail eggs also have a relatively more affordable price compared to the price of duck eggs and purebred chicken eggs. In addition to quail eggs, livestock products that are still difficult or rarely found are quail culls. According to Sarjana, et al (2010), cull quail is quail meat that can be consumed. Male quail that do not pass the selection as superior males and female quail whose productivity has decreased are categorized as cull quail.

The sale of quail eggs and meat products can increase cash income for farmers. The business opportunity was carried out by the Pesantren Manajer Tholabie. Although both are Islamic educational institutions, both boarding schools can take advantage of business opportunities, as well as the wealth of human resources (students) and natural resources (land). With business competition between Islamic boarding schools and competing quail breeders in Jembrana and Malang, Indonesia. Islamic boarding schools must have a good strategy in developing quail farming businesses. Therefore, research related to formulating quail farming business development strategies based on the strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities and threats of each pesantren needs to be done.

The purpose of the research is to analyze internal factors consisting of strengths, and weaknesses as well as external factors consisting of opportunities and threats of each pesantren and can formulate a good development strategy for pesantren in facing threats and minimizing weaknesses so that pesantren can continue to be sustainable in quail farming and can be economically independent.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Development Strategy

Strategy is a planning process that involves setting the organization's long-term goals and objectives, as well as setting a series of steps and allocating the resources needed to achieve these goals (Purwanti, 2019). Meanwhile, according to Siswondo and Agustina (2021), strategy is an effort made to achieve success and achieve goals. A development strategy is an action taken to achieve effectiveness in achieving organizational goals, with a focus on achieving good cooperation between individuals and

organizations (Siagian, 2000). The development strategy is also explained by Shobirin and Ali (2019), that the development strategy is the details of the steps that must be taken to achieve the goals.

Quail Farming

The quail farming business has several advantages such as not requiring a large area of land, so it can be done by various groups, both small and large scale, including commercial scale (Randell and Gerry, 2008). Another advantage of quail farming is that quails are a good source of animal protein to fulfill human nutritional needs and have the fastest production cycle among other poultry such as ducks and chickens where within 40-45 days, quail production can reach 250-300 eggs/head/year with an average weight of 10g/grain. However, in addition to the advantages of quail farming, there are also disadvantages, namely one of the problems is that less than optimal growth can cause variations in body weight and egg production. In addition, sometimes there are demands from consumers who want quail eggs with low cholesterol levels and high nutritional content. (Basri and Sulastri, 2020).

Data Analysis

SWOT analysis is an evaluation assessment of internal factors, namely the strengths and weaknesses of an organization, as well as an assessment of external factors, namely opportunities and threats from the environment (Griffin, 2004). IE (Internal-External) Matrix Analysis according to Rangkuti (2016), there is an IE (Internal-External) matrix which is divided into 6 quadrants, namely:

		TOTAL INTERNAL SCORE						
		4,0	Strong	3,0	Average	2,0	Weak	1,0
TOTAL EXTERNAL SCORE	High	I Growth		II Growth		III Rentrenchment		
	Medium	IV Stability		V Growth		VI Rentrenchment		
	Low	VII Growth		VIII Growth		IX Rentrenchment		
	3,0							
	2,0							
	1,0							

Figure 1. IE Matrix
Source: Rangkuti (2016)

SWOT matrix is a decision-making tool to determine logically executed strategies that optimize strengths and opportunities, but at the same time minimize the weaknesses and threats of a business. (Setyorini, et al 2016). The flow in compiling the SWOT matrix is as follows:

- a) Formulate business unit opportunities and threats as well as its internal strengths and weaknesses
- b) Build a SO (Strength Opportunity) strategy by combining internal strengths and external opportunities.
- c) Build a WO (Weakness Opportunity) strategy by matching internal weaknesses with external opportunities.
- d) Develop an ST (Threat Strength) strategy by combining internal strengths and external threats.
- e) Develop a WT (Threat Weakness) strategy by combining internal weaknesses and external threats.

The SWOT matrix is:

Table 1. SWOT Matrix

EFAS	IFAS	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESS
OPPORTUNITIES		SO Strategy	WO Strategy
THREATS		ST Strategy	WT Strategy

Source: David in Nourlette and Hati, 2017.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Profile of Pesantren Manajer Tholabie

Pesantren Manajer Tholabie is one of the boarding schools in Malang City which is engaged in religious academics and has a business unit in the livestock sector. PPMT is a student boarding school with a type of modern/khalafiyah boarding school. A khalafiyah (modern) boarding school is a boarding school that can develop its own education program with a curriculum composed of formal, informal, and non-formal education (Tolib, 2015).

Internal External Factor

Table 2. Strengths Score Calculation

Strengths	Weight	Rating	Score
Can utilize and develop natural resources and human resources well	0,07	5	0,35
Good availability and continuity of quail egg products	0,06	4	0,24
Can utilize social media marketing as a form of marketing	0,06	4	0,24
The services provided by the boarding school to consumers are very good	0,09	4	0,36
The boarding school has increased capacity from both economic and social aspects	0,09	5	0,45
Increased interaction of the boarding school with external (community, and other communities)	0,06	4	0,24
Santri can improve their skills in quail cultivation, financial management, marketing management	0,08	5	0,4
The boarding school gained new relationships	0,05	3	0,15
The location of the cage is far from the community	0,07	4	0,28
Can utilize waste to become economic value	0,07	5	0,35
Delivery service available	0,07	4	0,28
Sub Total	0,77		3,34

Source: Primary data processed, 2023.

Table 3. Calculation of Weakness Score

Weakness	Weight	Rating	Score
Incomplete recording	0,05	2	0,1
Closed data on the development of quail farming to the University of Brawijaya	0,06	2	0,12
Lack of support from the local government	0,05	1	0,05
The boarding school did not convey the existing problems of quail farming to Bank Indonesia and Brawijaya University	0,07	2	0,14
Sub Total	0,23		0,41
Total	1		3,75

Source: Primary data processed, 2023.

Based on the results of the evaluation analysis of internal factors, it shows that the Strengths factor has a score of 3.34 and the Weakness factor with a score of 0.41. This figure shows that quail farming in Pesantren Manajer Tholabie has strong internal strengths, and there are low weaknesses that need to be anticipated.

Table 4. Opportunity Score Calculation

Opportunity	Weight	Rating	Score
Development and advancement of science and technology	0,06	5	0,3
High access to market information	0,08	4	0,32

Opportunity	Weight	Rating	Score
High consumer demand that makes boarding schools have to become resellers and producers	0,09	5	0,45
Customer loyalty	0,08	4	0,32
Availability of livestock production facilities sellers to fulfill cultivation needs	0,08	3	0,24
Increase in population	0,07	3	0,21
Market segmentation	0,08	4	0,32
Community support in quail farming	0,07	4	0,28
Sub Total	0,61		2,44

Source: Primary data processed, 2023.

Table 5. Threat Score Calculation

Threat	Weight	Rating	Score
The existence of quail breeders in Malang, and Blitar	0,07	1	0,07
Lack of communication to PSBI partner farmers regarding quail conditions	0,07	2	0,14
Erratic climate change and the presence of pests	0,07	3	0,21
Lack of monitoring from Bank Indonesia on field conditions	0,09	2	0,18
Lack of success indicators from Bank Indonesia on PSBI	0,09	1	0,09
Sub Total	0,39		0,69
Total	1		3,13

Source: Primary data processed, 2023.

Based on the results of the evaluation analysis of external factors, it shows that the Opportunities factor has a score of 2.44 and the Threats factor with a weight score of 0.69. This figure shows the meaning that the quail farming business at Pesantren Manajer Tholabie has opportunities from a very large external environment and, there are threats that are small enough to need anticipation from Pesantren Manajer Tholabie.

IE Matrix

The IE matrix shows that the position of the quail farming business in the boarding school is in cell I. Conditions in cell I, the strategy that can be applied is Grow and Build.

Table 6. External Internal Matrix

		Total IFE Value weighted		
		Strong	Average	Weak
		3.0-4.0	2.0-2.99	1.0-1.99
Total EFE Weighted Values	High 3.0-4.0	I	II	III
	Medium 2.0-2.99	IV	V	VI
	Low 1.0-1.99	VII	VIII	IX

Source: Primary data processed, 2023.

SWOT Matrix

There is a collaboration of 4 strategies, namely the SWOT strategy by using strengths and taking advantage of opportunities to minimize threats and improve weaknesses. These strategies are:

- a) Looking for additional human resources and developing human resources with increased competence
- b) Utilization of other social media marketing in addition to the media that has been used
- c) Maintaining service to consumers

- d) Screening business capital and product development
- e) Increase the quail population to increase quail egg production
- f) Complete and routinize the filling of maintenance recordings
- g) Improve communication with experts, stakeholders and program organizers
- h) Designing the right marketing strategy
- i) Have the mindset to grow the business even bigger despite the absence of success indicators
- j) Maintain the quality of quail production

CONCLUSION

Based on the research, Pesantren Manajer Tholabie has an excellent position to develop a business in the field of quail farming. The strategy for developing quail farming at Pesantren Manajer Tholabie can be done by using a SWOT strategy that can make Pesantren Manajer Tholabie pay more attention to shortcomings and minimize future threats by utilizing its strengths and opportunities to compete in the market.

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